

PROBLEMS OF LEGAL REGULATION OF PERSONAL DATA
PROTECTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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***Abstract.** The article discloses the legal aspects of personal data and their protection, classification within the framework of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, the need for personal data protection, factors affecting it, issues related to data privacy and existing problems regarding the guarantees of the rights of the owner of personal data are highlighted.*

***Keywords:** Personal data, encryption of personal data, identification of personal data, regular security audits, privacy of personal data, cybercrimes related to personal data, priority of the rights and interests of the owner of personal data.*

In today's age of digital technology, the issue of protecting information about an individual is gaining global importance. As a result of the rapid development and widespread use of modern information and communication technologies, the processes of collection, processing and storage of personal data are becoming more complex Day by day. This, in turn, makes the issue of legal regulation of information about the person relevant.

After independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing consistent reforms to ensure the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens,

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including the inviolability of personal life. The personal data Act, passed in 2019, was one of the important steps taken in this direction. However, the rapid development of digital technologies and the processes of global integration are creating new challenges and challenges in this area.

The relevance of the study is that the comprehensive study of the problems that exist in the field of legal regulation of information about an individual, the analysis of international experience and the development of ways to improve national legislation are some of the most important tasks of today. Particular emphasis is placed on individual data protection issues in trans-border data transmission, artificial intelligence technologies, and Big Data (Big Data) Processing. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan specifically mentions the protection of the rights and legal interests of citizens. The protection of the privacy and interests of every person is of great importance, and the state takes legal protection of this through its legislative documents. If we take into account the fact that information communications are expanding and taking a special place in every person's life and any information is spreading in seconds, it is necessary to further strengthen the legislation in this regard, to constantly develop methods of legal protection of violated rights and legitimate interests. Because the Internet and other social expansion has caused a sharp increase in the exchange of information between people and organizations. In addition, various interstate integrations have created the need for further improvement of legal regulation in this regard. After all, by the 21st century, not only the market of goods and services, but also the information market began to develop in society. It is worth noting that the scope of distribution, collection and processing of information is taking on new forms.

When personal information is being formed, it is also important for what purpose it is collected and processed. After all, the legality, truthfulness, reliability and purposefulness of the actions taken to collect, systematize, store, change, fill in, use, give, distribute, transfer, appropriate and destroy personal data are always

relevant. Pursuant to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Personal data" adopted on July 2, 2019, personal data — information recorded on electronic, paper and (or) other tangible media relating to a specific individual or giving the possibility of his identification [1]. Some authors try to interpret the concept of personal data within the framework of the concept provided by the current legislation [2. -118 p.].

According to Kha.A. Paluaniyazov, "personal information" is information that describes a specific natural person, his or her physical and social status, which is available in an open or closed manner in civil transactions, is important in the implementation and protection of civil rights [3]. According to some literature, personal information is information related to a specific person or personal data subject[4]. Personal information is considered by M.R. Mikheeva as information about a specific person [5]. According to I. Nasriev, personal information is any identifiable or identifiable information related to a natural person" [6]. It's no secret that all aspects of society are digitized, information circulation is expanding, and the process of evaluating, selling, and disposing of information as a commodity is expanding. Because in the digital world, as information technologies play an increasingly important role in our daily lives, personal data is becoming a "valuable asset". But ensuring their security and privacy is undoubtedly the main concern for its owner and handlers. In this regard, the collection, processing, and storage of personal data not only by government agencies, but also by companies creates the need to protect this data from threats and attackers. It should be understood that the importance of personal data protection is not only the above, but also important for human life and activity, and is a special factor in its protection. Personal data is a collection of sensitive information about each individual. Therefore, it is necessary to always understand the importance of this information for its owner. Usually, as personal data is collected and processed by authorized government agencies and some companies, it is their duty to protect it.

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If personal information is disclosed to third parties, it may lead to fraud, defamation and other serious problems. The need to protect personal data is determined by a number of factors. Including:

Dangers and threats. The collection and processing of personal data involves risks and threats. Cybercriminals can use vulnerabilities in security systems to gain access to personal data, access the resources they are stored on, or access the memory of the computers where it is stored and use it for criminal purposes . Data leaks, viruses, and other cyberattacks have become ubiquitous problems on the Internet. According to T. L. Tropina, "cybercrimes are violations of data confidentiality, unauthorized access to computers and computer networks, violations of the confidentiality of trade secret information, computer conspiracy (interference with operation, data modification, destruction, etc.), economic cyber attacks (in particular, computer fraud) are divided into types [7].

Encryption of personal data. Encryption of personal data is a method of data protection in which data is converted into an encrypted form that is accessible only to authorized users using a key. It is considered an important mechanism to protect data in transit and storage.

Identification of personal data . It is important to register and identify personal data in a computer system. It can be a number or a string of characters naming the subjects of the relationship related to the protection of personal data. This information is called a subject identifier. If a user has an identifier registered in the network, he is a legal (legitimate) user, otherwise an illegal (illegal) user. Before using computer resources, the user must go through the identification and authentication process of the computer system. Identification is the process of identifying the user by his identity (name) in relation to personal data. This is the first function that is executed when a user tries to access the network. The user informs the system of his identity upon his request, and the system checks its

presence in its database. Only if all the data match, the keeper of the personal data makes it possible to use it.

Multi-factor authentication. Authentication is the basis of any system security, which consists of verifying the authenticity of user data by the server[8]. It is worth noting that the verification process may be completely different depending on the circumstances. For example, to access a stored information source, you need to open it with a key, password. In this example, the key, the password, acts as an identifier. The process of opening (matching a key and a cipher) is authentication. In the virtual world, this is similar to going through the authentication stage (checking the entered password). However, today there are one-factor and two-factor authentication. Two-factor authentication means a second password, a lock that improves additional information security. Nowadays, the word authentication also means electronic authentication, that is, the procedure for accessing websites, electronic wallets, programs, etc. Using multi-factor authentication adds an additional layer of protection by requiring users to provide not only a password, but also an additional factor to log in (such as a one-time code, fingerprint, eye, or facial recognition).

Regular security checks. Regular security checks allow you to identify vulnerabilities and respond to them before attackers use them to launch an attack.

User education. Increasing user awareness of cyber security can help prevent fraud and cyber attacks. Users should be trained on how to identify potential threats and be careful when providing personal information.

Compliance with the law on the protection of personal data. Strict compliance with the laws and local regulations related to the protection of personal data helps to ensure data security and protect the rights of users. The protection of personal data is the responsibility of each person who collects and processes this data. Data security is a key aspect of our digital world. The above-mentioned factor helps to reduce the risks associated with illegal acquisition, processing and

disclosure of personal data and to ensure data privacy. Effective protection of personal data is the guarantee of users' trust and confidence in the use of modern technologies and services.

In order to protect personal data, it is important to define their scope. For example, some authors include information about a person, such as lifestyle, that can explain the identity of a certain person[9], while some authors also include mother's maiden name, medical history, and insurance policy information in the personal information sentence[10]. Some literature even recognizes genetic and ethnic origin, ideological beliefs, or trade union membership as personal data[11]. If we rely on such considerations, we can understand without hesitation that the considerations for categorizing personal data are incomplete.

According to I. Zakirov, protection of rights is carried out within the framework established by the law, that is, using a certain form, method and means of protection. There are two forms of rights protection - jurisdictional (through court) and non-jurisdictional (without court)[12]. In fact, the protection of personal data can use different tools and methods. It can also be categorized into jurisdictional and non-jurisdictional defenses in harmony with the above point. is manifested in the activity of competent state bodies in the protection of violated or conflicting rights . Its essence is that a person whose rights related to personal data have been violated (data owner, custodian, owner, operator) applies to the authorized state body to restore his rights. Rules related to administrative procedures are used here [13]. Basically, the violated rights are protected in the procedures and conditions stipulated in the procedural legislation, rules of procedure.

The form of jurisdictional protection of personal data, in turn, has general (judicial) and special (administrative procedures) procedures for protecting violated rights. Judicial protection is carried out through state and non-state courts (arbitration courts, commercial arbitrations). The special procedure is the

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protection in the administrative procedure. This applies only as an exception to the general rule, that is, in cases directly specified by law. Non-legal form of protection of personal data means that the person whose right has been violated acts independently and of his own free will without referring to the state or other authorized body. However, the protection must be implemented on the basis of certain conditions.

For example, according to Article 13 of the FC, the methods of protection of civil rights by a person should be equal to the level of violation of the right and should not go beyond the scope of actions necessary to prevent the violation of the right. In addition, personal data protection can be divided into private and public legal protection. If there is a need to protect personal data through private-civil-legal grounds, then the legal basis of such protection can be connected with the methods provided for in Article 11 of the Civil Code. The state guarantees the protection of personal data through its adopted legislation. These guarantees are implemented by competent authorities and ensure that a number of measures are taken to protect data. The measures taken by the owner and (or) the operator, as well as the third party to protect personal data, consist of legal, organizational and technical measures. Legal, organizational and technical measures are legal, organizational and technical measures to exercise the subject's right to be protected from interference in his/her personal life, to keep personal data whole and complete, to observe data confidentiality, and to prevent illegal processing of data.

27¹ of the Law "On Personal Data", special conditions for processing personal data of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan were established. Based on it, the owner and (or) the operator collects and systematizes the personal data of citizens of Uzbekistan using information technologies, including through the Internet, on technical devices physically located in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the personal databases registered in the state register of personal databases in the prescribed manner. and must ensure its preservation.

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Confidentiality of personal data is a requirement for the owner and (or) operator or other person who has gained access to personal data to comply with the requirement that it should not be disclosed and disseminated without the consent of the subject or other legal grounds. The owner and (or) operator and other persons who have gained access to personal data must not disclose or disseminate personal data without the consent of the subject (Article 28 of the Law on Personal Data). In other words, privacy of personal information is the protection of personal information about individuals from unauthorized access, use or disclosure. This issue is becoming more and more relevant in a digital era where a lot of personal information is stored and transmitted through various online services and platforms. The main aspects of privacy of personal data are as follows:

Data Collection and Use. Personal data entities and services must inform users about what data they collect and how they plan to use that data. Users must consent to the collection and processing of their data.

Data security . Personal data subjects must take measures to protect stored personal data from unauthorized access, hacking or leakage. This may include encryption, authentication mechanisms and other technical measures.

Data storage . Personal data should only be kept for as long as necessary and deleted at the end of their useful life. This relieves the unnecessary responsibility of storing unnecessary collected data.

User rights. Users have the right to know how information about them is stored and used, and to access and correct their information.

Transfer of data to third parties. The transfer of personal data to third parties (for example, advertisers or partners) should be carried out only with the consent of the user and on the basis of legal restrictions.

Legislation. Many countries have laws governing the collection, use, and protection of personal information, such as the General Data Protection Regulation in the European Union or the Personal Data Privacy Act in the United States.

Responsibility . Organizations are responsible for compliance with privacy regulations and may be subject to fines or sanctions for violations.

The owner, operator and other persons authorized to use personal data must not disclose and distribute this data to third parties without the consent of the data owner. In order to provide the population with information, sources of personal information that can be used by everyone can be created. Personal information that is freely available on the basis of consent or that is not subject to confidentiality requirements is publicly available information.

Publicly available personal information is information about an individual that can be made publicly available or distributed without restriction. Unlike sensitive personal information, which requires special protection and consent for use, publicly available information can be obtained from open sources and used without breach of confidentiality. For example, first and last name: if a person independently posts his name in public resources such as social networks or public profiles, it becomes publicly available information.

Examples include contact information (e-mail address or phone number that an individual provides for public access), professional information (workplace, title, and other details about work activities that you share in public sources or professional platforms), educational information (citizen publicly available information about the school, university or educational courses he/she has decided to study), projects and achievements (if a person publishes his projects, research, articles or other achievements in public sources), social networks (posts, comments posted on public pages in social networks and information), public records (for example, public registers, databases, news articles and information from other sources available to the public), etc. It should be noted that even publicly available personal information can be used with respect for human privacy and ethical standards. When working with such data, it is necessary to take into account its context, to give people sufficient information about how and for what purposes

their data will be used. The subject has the right to enter information into publicly available sources of personal information based on written consent. Information about the subject can be removed from publicly accessible sources of information about the person at his request, in the form in which the consent was given, or in written form, including in the form of an electronic document, as well as according to the decision of the competent state body or court.

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